

smFISH: signal amplification with SABER

Short name: smFISH_SABER

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Abstract: SABER enables programmable amplification by generating longer oligos with repeated binding sites for secondary imaging oligos. More information can be found in the original paper (Kishi *et al.*, 2019). We use these amplicons not on the primary oligos but attached to the barcode oligos from the ORCA approach (Bintu *et al.*, 2018). We also employ this approach in sequential smFISH, as the amplified oligos can be stripped (see the separate protocol). To reduce background while maintaining protocol compatibility with the fluidics system, we employ a 3-stage hybridization strategy to optimize stringency for each step.

- **Primary probes:** more stringent hybridization of (1X, 30% formamide, 10% dextran) instead of our usual (2X, 20% formamide).
- **SABER-Amplicons:** buffer with (2xSSC, 20% Formamide, 10% dextran), dextran for reduced background and lower probe concentration.
- **Imager:** A low-stringency buffer (2X SSC, 10% formamide, 10% dextran) was used to preserve oligo binding, likely due to the low T_m of the G-free imager; dextran enables reduced fluorophore concentration.

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1 General points

- We found that the imagers can **carry two fluorophores** (3' and 5'). This leads to a signal increase.
- For moderate amplification (3X sites), oligos up to 84 nts can be directly purchased (IDT). These oligos are inexpensive and enable rapid experimentation.

2 Materials

2.1 Reagents

Isothermal Buffer 10X	M0537 NEB
MgSO4 100mM	M0537 NEB
dATP 10mM	U1330 Promega
dCTP 10mM	U1330 Promega
dTTP 10mM	U1330 Promega
Clean.G 10 μ M 10mM	CCCCGAAAGTGGCCTCGGGCCTTTTGGCCCGAGGCCACTTTCG
Hairpin 100 μ M	40-45bp
Bst LF Pol 8U/ μ L	M0537 NEB
OLIGOS	40bp
MiniElute columns	28004 Qiagen

2.2 Oligos

We order all oligos from IDT unless specified otherwise. Indicated prices are only indicative.

2.2.1 Nomenclature

- All oligos targeting a specific gene carries an additional sequence termed "**readout X**".
- The amplified SABER oligos carry the complementary sequence to this **readout sequence**. We refer to these oligos as **readouts RO_x**, where the X indicates against which readout they are designed.
- SABER proposed different hairpin sequence (HP) that can be amplified, these are referred to as **HP_Y** where Y is an index from the original paper, e.g. we often use HP₂₇.
- Readout oligos also carry a toehold sequence that allows stripping them to remove the signal.
- Imager oligos are specific against the amplicons obtained from the used HP.

2.3 Equipment

- PCR machine
- Electrophoresis system with camera

2.4 Buffers

For one 12 mm coverslip washed in a 24-well plate, we usually use

Buffer	Day 1	Day 2
2X SSC	2 mL	2 mL
Wash buffer I	1 mL	2 mL
Wash buffer II	-	3 mL
Wash buffer III	-	3 mL

2.4.1 Wash buffers

For 10mL, adjust accordingly for your experiment.

Reagent	2X SSC	Wash I 1X SSC 30% F	Wash II 1X SSC 20% F	Wash III 2X SSC 10% F
20XSSC	1 mL	0.5 mL	0.5 mL	1 mL
Formamide		3 mL	2 mL	1 mL
H2O DEPC	9 mL	6.5 mL	7.5 mL	8 mL

2.4.2 Hybridization buffers

- ▲ Buffers with **different stringency** are used to hybridize primary probes, SABER probes, and imager oligos.
- ▲ When using SABER on a fluidic system, we only use 5% Dextran. Otherwise, the buffers become too viscous.
- ▲ When using SABER on the fluidics system, we use EC to hybridize SABER and imager oligos.

Reagent		Primary Probe	SABER Probe	Imager-HPy
20XSSC		50 μ L	50 μ L	100 μ L
Formamide or EC (bench/fluidics)		300 μ L (F/F)	200 μ L (F / EC)	100 μ L (F / EC)
Dextran 40%	10% bench	250 μ L	250 μ L	250 μ L
	5% fluidic system	125 μ L	125 μ L	125 μ L
Triton 10%		10 μ L	10 μ L	10 μ L
H2O DEPC: adjust to 1mL		400 / 525 μ L	500 / 625 μ L	550 / 575 μ L

2.4.2.1 Hybridization buffer for primary oligos

See the base protocol; for example, when using oPools, we use 1 μ L for 50 μ L of hybridization buffer.

2.4.2.2 Hybridization buffer for SABER probes

- The goal is to adjust to a final concentration of the amplicon.
- Prepare SABER-stock solution (below): **1 μ L for 50 μ L hybridization buffer**

Reagent	Amount	Comment
SABER-RO _x -HP _y	... μ L (adjust)	Depends on the amplification, target is 40 pmol .
10X NEB3	1 μ L	
H2O DEPC	... μ L	Adjust water accordingly for total volume of 10 μ L.
Total	10 μL	

2.4.2.3 Hybridization buffer for imaging probes

- Prepare imager stock solution (see below): 1 μ L per 50 μ L hybridization Buffer

Reagent	Amount
Imager HPY-CyZ (100 μ M)	5 μ L
10X NEB3	1 μ L
H2O DEPC	4 μ L

3 Methods

3.1 Important considerations

Due to the (strong) signal amplification, individual dots that stem from either non-specific primary probes or amplicons can be seen in the image. To reduce this non-specific signal, hybridization and washing conditions were established that are also compatible with fluidics system.

3.2 Saber amplification

Amplicons can be prepared before and stored, or as mentioned above shorter amplicons can be bought directly.

3.2.1 Prepare amplification mix

1. Prepare mix for 100 μL (see below)
2. Heat the mix @ 37°C for 15 min.
3. Add 10 μL Primer Oligo ROX-HP-Y (10 μM).

Buffer	Amount	Final concentration
Isothermal Buffer 10X	10 μL	1X
MgSO ₄ 100mM	10 μL	10 mM
dATP 10mM	5 μL	500 μM
dCTP 10mM	5 μL	500 μM
dTTP 10mM	5 μL	500 μM
Clean.G 10 μM 10mM	1 μL	100nM
Hairpin 100 μM	1 μL	1 μM
Bst LF Pol 8U/ μL	5 μL	30 U
H ₂ O	48 μL	

3.2.2 Amplification

▲ CRITICAL STEP: length of oligo is proportional to amplification time

1. Incubate at 37°C.
2. Elongation is proportional to the amplification time. For an elongation of 30 min, we obtain oligos of around 200 bases (8-10 repeats).
3. Stop the reaction with 10 min @ 80°C
4. Purify amplified oligos on MiniElute columns.
5. Elution volume: 10 μL (Elution buffer from the kit).
6. Check amplicons on a 2% agarose gel in TAE (Volume = 1 μL).
7. Estimate the concentration of the probe obtained by comparison with a RO at 20 μm .

Gel on the right shows ladder (first and last column), and oligos from IDT with different number of repeats (X1, X3) and different amplification times (30 min and 2h).

3.3 Day 1-2: fixation, permeabilization, primary probe hybridization

- Follow the base protocol for sample processing up to the step to hybridize primary probes.
- **▲ CRITICAL STEP:** use more stringent hybridization conditions for primary probes (1X SSC, 30% formamide) instead of our usual (2X SSC, 20% formamide).

3.4 Day 3: SABER amplification on the bench

1. **Wash after primary probe hybridization**
 - a. Wash twice with wash buffer I, incubate @ 37C for 30 min.
 - b. Wash once with wash buffer II, incubate @ RT for 10 min.
2. **Hybridization of SABER probes**

3. Incubate at 37°C for 30 min in Hybridization buffer (Saber-Probe), protected from light.
 - a. Wash twice with wash buffer II, incubate at 37°C for 30 min.
 - b. Wash once with wash buffer III, incubate at RT for 5 min.
4. **Hybridization of imager oligos.**
5. Incubate at 37°C for 30 min in Hybridization buffer (Imager).
6. Wash twice with wash buffer III, incubate at 37°C for 30 min.
7. **Final washes, DAPI staining, and mounting.**
 - a. Wash once with 2X SSC, incubate at RT for 5 min.
8. Wash once with DAPI buffer, incubate at RT for 10 min.
 - a. Wash once with 2X SSC, incubate at RT for 10 min.
 - b. Mount with Prolonggold.

3.5 Day 3: SABER amplification for autoFISH

- The main differences are in the composition and volumes of the buffers.
- Formamide is replaced by Ethylene Carbonate (at the same percentage), and the Dextran concentration is reduced to 5%.
- The volumes are to be adjusted. A probe volume of 2 mL in hybridization buffer is required to hybridize a run of fluidic.

4 References

Bintu, B. *et al.* (2018) 'Super-resolution chromatin tracing reveals domains and cooperative interactions in single cells', *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, 362(6413). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aau1783>.

Kishi, J.Y. *et al.* (2019) 'SABER amplifies FISH: enhanced multiplexed imaging of RNA and DNA in cells and tissues', *Nature Methods*, 16(6), pp. 533–544. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-019-0404-0>.

5 Version history and archiving

Version	Date	Modified by	Changes
v1	31.10.2024	Mueller F, Weber C	Initial version.
v2	1.7.2025	Mueller F, Weber C	Resubmission of autoFISH paper. Improved for clarity.